

Using games in Communicative Language Teaching.

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Annotatsiya

Teaching today has changed a lot over the past years. Once it was all about learners being passive and listening in the classroom, but today learners are usually much more active in the classroom, and what better way to be active than by playing games (Steve Sugar.1998.p. 3).

Almost everybody loves playing whether they are young or old. From early childhood playing is an enormous part of most children's lives and it plays a big part of their development as well. When playing most games participants are almost forced into communicating with each other in order for the game to work. The need for communication during games, and the informal setting games provide encourages students to be unafraid to talk, which practices their fluency, a valuable communication skill.

Kalit so'zlar:

Communicative teaching, competent, exposed to the language, content and methods, the necessary language material, intensive methodological equipment, communicative skills, standards of content material selection, English language instructors.

The national curriculum for foreign languages emphasizes the importance of learning languages and especially the importance of communication. Because of this fact it is vitally important for teachers to create a positive learning environment, and to try to spark interest amongst their students both in the foreign language and culture because that is important to a successful language learning process. Games help achieve these goals as they help satisfy the requirement of the national curriculum that language learning should be enjoyable for students (Aðalnámsskrá Grunnskóla. Erlend mál.2007.p. 6).

Why games?

There are a number of reasons that games deserve a place in the language classroom.

First of all, they are fun, which is extremely important, because they can help activate students who may have been inactive before, due to lack of interest.

Second, games also play a big part in helping participants build relationships, and to feel equal. .

Third, the reason most people want to learn a language is to be able to use it in real situations, for example when travelling. Also that allows students to do more on their own, and that can very well result in an increase in their confidence level. (Langran & Purcell.1994. p.12-14).

Fourth, language students need to be exposed to the language in a variety of situations, which is a need games can fulfill. N

Fifth, language students need to be emotionally involved, meaning they need to feel something while they are exposed to the language. Strong emotions, such as happiness, excitement, amusement and suspense allow students to feel positively about their learning situation and are therefore likely to have a positive effect on language learning.

Sixth, games can be a good strategy when teaching various subjects because they are very likely to spark interest amongst students. They can be used with students of all ages, and when they are used with other teaching methods they create diversity which is ideal for school work (Ingvar Sigurgeirsson.1999.p. 80).

Finally, using games in the classroom is important because many children do not get enough opportunity to play during their free time, which can be traced to the rapid changes in our society. Cities are getting bigger and traffic is getting heavier which means that more and more parents are hesitant to let their children play outside. Also passive activities such as watching television, or the computer screen are seen as being more exciting than actually physically playing, so today the sight of children playing various games in groups outside is becoming much more rare than it was 10, 15 or 20 years ago. This is not a good development, and it can have several bad consequences for our society. One possible consequence is that the lack of movement can cause health problems because even though not all games are physical some certainly are (Masheder.1989.p. 3). Another consequence this change might have is decreased social skills because, according to Piaget, children's games reflect society and that by playing games children learn many of society's rules and regulations (Cole, Cole & Lightfoot. 2005.p. 536).

Games play considerable role in teaching English. The aims and tasks of teaching English, the content and methods can't be achieved without repeating and systematizing the necessary language material.

In his/her work the teacher uses various types of methods and techniques. The teacher must have a good professional level knowledge of the field and a great leadership potential. He teaches the pupils' and students' pronunciation, lexis, grammar, reading, speaking and writing. Great attention is paid to the developing of unprepared speech habits. The main objective of the learner is to be able to use the linguistic material to express his thoughts. The teacher should encourage each pupil to speak on the subject in his/her own way and thus develop pupils' initiative and thinking. There are many techniques for stimulating pupils' unprepared speech. And the teacher must choose the techniques most suitable for the pupils and students since he knows their progress in the language, the concrete material at which pupils and students are working.

Here we can't help speaking about the games which arouse pupils' interest to the language; they make the atmosphere of the lesson more emotional, more lively. They give the possibility to even a weak pupil to take an active part in the game.

There are different kinds of games: lexical, grammar, role plays, the ABC games, phonetics games and so on.

I would like to introduce some small games which English teachers can use in their class.

Introduction game: "Stating the names" where students sit in a circle and one by one they introduce themselves, but the only catch is that before saying their own name they always have to repeat the names of the students who have already introduced themselves, and as the game progresses it gets harder and harder for students to memorize all the names (Ingvar Sigurgeirsson.1995.p. 28-29). In order to make this game more fitting in a language classroom the teacher could ask the student to add something they like that starts with the same letter as their name, for example "my name is Anna and I love apples". Another idea could be to have students add adjectives with the same letter as their names, for example "Sigga super" or "Anna awesome" and that way it teaches adjectives as well. A good idea could be to allow them to find adjectives that begin with the same letter as the second, or even third one in their name.

"Hot-seat" - a student seats with his/her back to the board or to the teacher. The teacher displays a word or a flash card, other students describe what is on the card to enable the student guess what it is. For higher level students teachers can make hot-seat more challenging by writing a number of TABOO WORDS on the board. For example if a teacher shows the students a flash card of say a HAIRDRESSER. Taboo words could be words like CUT & HAIR. Students cannot use these two words to describe hairdresser. This forces the students to find other ways of describing the word without the taboo words. Taboo words are most often words that can easily make give away the word of the flashcard.

Guessing Game "What Am I?"

For this game you will need to put a sticker on the back of each student, with a noun written on it, for example, apple, chair, Wednesday, bathroom, or bottle of tomato ketchup. The students have to mingle with one another and ask questions to find out 'What am I...?'

Students can only reply with either 'Yes' or 'No'. Once they have found out what they are, they report to you and tell you what they are and what questions they had to ask in order to work it out. They could then go and write down the different questions. This also works when you use celebrity names instead of nouns – as long as all the students are aware of exactly who all the celebrities are. You could also use specific vocabulary sets such as countries ('Am I north of the equator, or south?'), or clothes ('Am I worn on the head?') The sky's the limit! Good for question forms and to get students talking.

The next game is called **"The Invitation"**. One of the pupils leaves the classroom. The rest of the pupils decide where they are going to go. Pupil 1 must guess their decision.

P1 – Let's go to the yard.

P2 - Thank you, I don't want.

P1 – Let's go to the cinema.

P3 - I am not well.

P1 – Let's go to my friend's birthday party.

P4 - Oh, with great pleasure.

In conclusion, teachers should not be afraid to play with children, because the game arouses children's interest to English, their outlook, even the weak pupil can remember the words and grammar structures through the game. Neither the teachers nor the students would like to have the experience of dull and boring class atmosphere, therefore, as a qualified ESL teacher, to well mastering some small games is of great necessity, which will bring you smile and laugh while teaching, especially for the beginner and elementary English learners, for if taught in a fun and creative way, they would love to enter the classroom and have your class. The teacher must know the aims and tasks of each game. It would be a nice beginning of his or her English learning journey.

REFERENCES:

1. *Aðalnámsskrá Grunnskóla. Erlend mál* (2007) Reykjavík: Menntamálaráðuneytið.
2. Cole, Michael. Cole, Sheila.R & Lightfoot, Cynthia (2005). *The development of children (5útgáfa)*. New York: Worth Publishers.
3. Ingvar Sigurgeirsson (1999). *Að mörgu er að hyggja*. Reykjavík: Æskan ehf.
4. Langran, John & Purcell, Sue (1994). *Language Games and Activities* [Rafræn heimild].
5. Mashedor, Mildred (1989). *Let's play together*. London: Green Print
6. Rixon, Shelagh (1981). *How to use Games in Language Teaching*. London: The Macmillan Press Ltd.
7. Purland, Matt (2004) *Big activity book*. UK by English Banana.com
8. Steve Sugar (1998). *Games That Teach*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Pfeiffer.